

Youth Entrepreneurship in Indian Scenario

P. A. Kavitha

*Assistant Professor, Pachamuthu College of Arts and Science for Women
Dharmapuri*

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Abstract

By 2017, World Bank estimates that there will be about 4 billion youths less than 25 years old and a big portion of that will be in India. Many young people cannot find employment. This has become particularly acute since the education explosion in early 2000's. These outcomes are both inefficient and inequitable. Evidence shows that the unemployed are unhappier, more likely to experience a range of health issues, and face difficulties in integrating back into the labour market place. The development of Indian society in general and the growth of the economy in large, requires the strong empowerment of youth. In developing economy like India, promotion of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship has become a priority for the government, financial institutions and academic institutions. One potential way of integrating young people into the global economy is to increase youth entrepreneurship. The objective is simple - to understand youth entrepreneurship and its role with focus on Indian scenario.

Introduction

The role of entrepreneurship plays in the socio-economic development of a country is well acknowledged. A large number of programmes to support entrepreneurship by government and international organisations. Youth entrepreneurship is gained more importance in recent years in many countries.

India is one of the fastest growing economies in the world. It needs to minimise barriers and provide support that will accelerate entrepreneurial growth. Indian youth facing similar problems like lack of soft skills, lack to start own business. Government and local communities across the world have recognised to build prosperity and stimulate regional growth. The main factor for its growing attention is the increased number of unemployed young people. Youth entrepreneurship will not only help in reducing unemployment but they have own creative and destiny by starting the business as their own companies. Some of the barriers found in youth entrepreneurship like lack of capital, poor infrastructure, strict government regulations, lack of guidance and awareness etc.

It also offers societal benefits. Entrepreneurs create jobs, increase innovation, raise competition and are responsive to changing economic opportunities and trends. Entrepreneurship offers other positive externalities. A young person setting up a new business may provide 'demonstration' or learning externalities in that they

may act as a role model for other young people. In India we have so many advantages of rich minerals, natural resources, forests, water bodies, marine resources and highest population though to accelerate the progress of economic growth through industrial development. During the periods of 1980's and till now industrial policy had encouraged small scale industry (SSI).

Entrepreneur and entrepreneurship has defined different authors in various ways.

Peter Drucker defines "it is one who always searches for change, respond to it and exploit it as an opportunity".

According to Schumpeter, 'an entrepreneur is a person who is willing and able to convert new idea or invention into a successful innovations'.

Objectives

The main objective of youth entrepreneurship to be developed by the more and more interesting job, freedom and autonomy in Indian scenario. Entrepreneurship is seen as a channel for the talents of mainly educated young people to explore their potential and cash their acumen. Becoming an entrepreneur offers benefits to young person through their human capital attributes (Self-reliance, skill development) and increasing the level of happiness.

The passion for going the entrepreneur way, outlining king - size ventures, intrinsic moves and the risk taking capacity to think, the government and the people need to take the drive come together and work to shine.

Importance of Youth Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is highly regarded as an important strategy to solve unemployment. Investing in entrepreneurial ventures and educating people to start-up those ventures can be an invaluable tool to advance human resources to promote socio- economic development. Therefore youth entrepreneurs have important role to play in the process of industrial as well as economic.

Successful entrepreneurs are likely to be optimistic, goal oriented and persistent. Entrepreneurs create new technologies, products and services to meet societies needs. Youth run enterprise provide valuable goods and services to society, especially the local community. Owing to the on-going GST, globalisation process youth entrepreneurship also promotes innovation and creative ideas, through experienced based learning.

Background Factors

Idea for establish

Starting new business means having a business idea must be based on concrete and structured plan. to evaluate the feasibility of the entrepreneurial idea through careful analysis of the product of its reference market. The Friends and relatives, Media coverage of business and business people, Ideas received from Training Programmes and Others.

Reason for Choosing as a Career

Many people opt for entrepreneurship as their career because their desire to be independent, some may to create Jobs for others , Inability to get desire jobs, Dislikes for the previous jobs, to earn more money and most of them to manage family business.

Family Role

Role model plays an important role because they function as carriers of value , emotions and experience towards employment. Young people whose parents own their business ventures may influence entrepreneurial attitudes for young people who live together in the same environment.

Access to Finance

The sources of capital for a business 50% make on their family funds, 20% from their own funds followed by loan from others and also from Financial institutions were SIDBI, IDBI, IFC, SFC, NAYE the major sources.

Government plays a vital role in creating a conducive atmosphere, taken many initiatives, launching many Programmes for development of young entrepreneurs. The lack of finance was also considered to be more severe barrier. The chances of creating a successful and sustainable business depends on assistance a young entrepreneurs obtains in the start - up and new business phases.

Social Cultural Constraints

Social and cultural backgrounds have important role on an individual approach to life. Culture is defined as a set of attitude, values and beliefs within a particular society. Thus social and cultural attitude influence the entrepreneurial activities of a population, a country region or ethnic group. Attitude not comes from ourselves but also from the environment.

Barriers in start of business

The success or failure of an enterprise dependent on overcoming potential barriers Examples are financial backing, adequate and guidance and Training. The lack of adequate access to finance and business support was the obstacles faced in starting up of the business. The regulative barriers are Tax rates, Subsidy Policy, Trade policy and others.

Risk and Fear

It was found that financial risk had a significant impact are Financial risk, Access to Finance, Social risks, Lack of Skills, Administrative Hurdles, Workload, Corruption, Competitions, and Market demand. It is considered to be important de -motivating factor for young entrepreneurs in setting up an enterprise.

Emphasis by The Family

The adventure and learning areas on which families emphasized laid upon on Education, Adventures, Honesty, Religion, Innovation, Learning, Independent, Hard Work.

Enhancing Entrepreneur skills

The Indian Government up to 1980-1990's did not encourage free entrepreneurship due to policy of mixed economy. But today we have from job seekers they were channelizing their creative skills and energy towards successful business ventures

Conclusion

The young entrepreneurs even though had other occupational opportunities, they chose entrepreneurship as a career because they aspire to earn more money. Most of the young entrepreneurs facing different problems of deficiency of working capital, tax regulations.

Today ,youth is more daring and hard working and career oriented. the country's government should create environment for business development. According to Indian scenario youth entrepreneurs share their past experience with social learners, mass media and communications should be used to create awareness about issues and problems encountered.

Our educational system also rarely exposes the students to become entrepreneur, he needs more aptitude to set up business. He / She is discouraged by adverse factors which arises lack of network, lack of mentoring support, lack of supportive system which hinders the emergence of entrepreneur in adequate measure.

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